

Lok Sabha Election 2014 and People's Participation.

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to visualise the participation of people in 2014 Lok Sabha election and the challenge of ticket distribution among congress and BJP parties. The Study is based on secondary source of data. The 2014 Lok Sabha Elections held in 9 phases on 7 April to 12 May 2014. The Lok Sabha Election of 2014 witnessed the record turnout of voters. The overall polling average has been recorded 66.38% which is the record in Lok Sabha Elections. The study provides a full length detail voter turnout and an over whelming majority was recorded. The study brings out the major highlights in case of majority voter turnout and severe seat winning transformation of the 2014 Lok Sabha Elections.

Key Words: Lok Sabha Elections 2014, voters, participation, turnout.

Introduction:

The Indian general Election 2014 was held to form the sixteenth Lok Sabha Electing members of parliament for all 543 parliamentary constituencies of India. Running in 9 phases from 7th April to 12 May 2014, this was the longest Election in the India's history. According to the Election commission of India, 814.5 million people were eligible to vote, with an increase of 100 million voters since the last general election in 2009 making this the largest ever Election in the world. Around 23.1 million eligible voters were aged 18 to 19 years. A total of 8251 candidates contested for the 543 Lok Sabha seats. The average election turnout over all nine phases was around 66.40%, the highest ever in the history of Indian general elections.

The result came a bit very soon as they were declared on 16th May 2014, fifteen days before the fifteenth Lok Sabha complete its term constitutional agreement on 31 May 2009. The counting exercise was held at 989 counting centres. The 545 seat lower house of parliament now has its first single party majority since 1984. Back then Elections ago, that majority belonged to the Indian National Congress. The National Democratic Alliances (NDA) led by Bhartiya Janta Party, won a wide-ranging victory taking 336 seats. The BJP itself won 282 seats, the first time

since Rajiv Gandhi's landslide victory in 1984 that an Indian Party has won enough seats to run without the support of other parties. The United Progressive Alliances (UPA) led by the Indian National Congress, won 59 seats, 44 of which won by congress. Congress remained behind to be the official opposition party, as to remain the official opposition party needs 55 seats won which was not managed by congress. Due to this fact, India remains without an official opposition party, as of 2019.

One more aspect which has made this 2014 Lok Sabha Election a point of debate is the emergence of Aam Aadmi Party (AAP). This new contestant has taken the center stage by grabbing people's mind with focusing on corruption and criminalization of politics.

Interestingly, there was always a group of political parties who neither wanted to be linked either UPA or NDA. Such parties were coming together as third front. This third front too was a success in the Indian political history on certain occasions. For this Lok Sabha Elections the third front is not amongst the major contenders or threats, but it still can cause damage at certain places.

One more dimensions which can be the highlight of the Lok Sabha Election 2014 is a new option given to the voters. The Election Commission of India has given the voters the right to reject all the candidates which are in the power struggle in any constituency. That means a voters can either vote for candidate he likes or simply say no to all of them. This option is called NOTA or none of the above.

This election emphasizes the importance of youth power. There is a very significant increase in the number of new voters in our country. As we all know once a person's age is of eighteen years, he or she is eligible to vote (before sixty first Amendment 1989 this limit was 21 years). For this election, there is an increase of whooping of ten corers (100 million) new voters. In other words, 100 million voters casted their vote for the first time in 2014 lok sabha election. This is why all political parties are seen trying to win their vote. Sudden increase in using the social media by political parties in India can be related to this youth factor.

Objectives

1. To study the challenges of ticket distribution among congress and BJP parties
2. To explore the people's participation in 2014 Lok Sabha Elections

Methodology:

This paper is mainly based on secondary data. For collection of secondary data, available literature in the form of books, newspapers, reports such Election Commission of India along with published articles and research papers have been selected.

Ticket distribution a big challenge for Congress and BJP Parties

The leadership of the state units of the two national parties in the state the congress and the BJP are going through a challenging phase with all and various eyeing for party ticket of the Lok Sabha Elections and the state leadership confined to playing a limited role in finalizing the list of candidates.

Interestingly, even those who lost the assembly election in mid-2013 are in search of ticket for the elections to the Lok Sabha, although knowing well that a bigger challenge lies ahead.

There are several ginger groups within the two parties complaining for ticket for their favorite candidates even as their large aim is to ensure that their party wins a major portion of seats. Much to the awkwardness of the leaders, party ticket is being fought on caste bases, although, at the beginning the plans are based on what is termed as win ability of the candidates. If the BJP use the term party loyal lists, the congress calls it "social engineering" although it should be noted that both the parties are keen on fielding candidates of a dominant community in some of the constituencies. While congress men are making a beeline to win the favour of the party high command, in the case of BJP, the aspirants are largely warming up to the state unit leaders to help them get party ticket for the elections.

The another matter that some candidates of the two parties are confident that they will get ticket and have even commenced their campaigning by meeting people and spending more time in the constituencies. Most of the aspirants for congress ticket believe that they have a good chance to win in present political scenario in the state.

Their view is clearly based on the situation where the Congress is ruling the state, unlike the predicament of the party, though heading the united progressive alliances government at the national level. It is in this center of the demand for party ticket that both the Congress and the BJP are expected to be rocked in the days to come, and topping this list in the struggle for ticket.

Participation of people in 2014 Lok Sabha Elections.

The 2014 Lok Sabha Elections saw an overwhelming participation of people in the elections, as this was a recordable voter turnout which the country saw. The 2014 Lok Sabha polls saw 66.38% voter turnout among the 827 million Indian electorates exercising their franchise, helping the country set an all-time voter turnout record. The polling percentage in the world's biggest democratic exercise comfortably surpassed the 1984 turnout 64%. When Rajiv Gandhi became the prime minister after the assassination of Indira Gandhi. Bhartiya Janta party Prime Minister nominee Narendra Modi wrote on micro blogging site twitter, "the biggest joy of 2014 elections has the increased turnout. Braving the scorching heat and the rain of people turned out in large numbers."

The 2014 polls also saw the record in terms of voter numbers set five years ago when the Congress led UPA returned to power for a second straight time. Altogether 551 million voters more than the combined population of the US, Germany, Canada and UK cast their ballots this year. The figure crushed the previous record of 417 million for any general election set five years ago after the 9 phase polling ends. The polling management body added 130 million more voters exercised their franchise than in the 2009, the country had seen 56.98 % voting. Majority of urban states like Delhi, Pune, Surat, Lucknow, Mumbai, Bangalore and Chandigarh recorded increased voting this year compared with the last time. Women voters also came out in large numbers and outnumbered their male counterparts in sixteen years including Arunachal Pradesh, Orissa, Punjab, Bihar and Uttarakhand.

Besides increased people's participation, the Lok Sabha elections of 2014 also happened to be the most expensive polls in the history of independent India, as it cost the state exchequer rupees 2428 crore. The 2009 general election had cost rupees 1483 that apart the election also seized the biggest cache of liquor, drugs and cash recorded during any election in the country.

In 2009 41.73 crores voters cast their vote and this time this number stands at 55.13 crore. This is an increase of 32 % in terms of absolute number of voters, about 15 states and all union territories. The excitement from elevations 2014 refuses to phase out. The country has voted, a party has now been elected to power and India is ready to walk a new path. The top highlights that marked the general election 2014 are discussed below.

1. The centre for media studies, an independent not for profit research organization has stated in several news media reports that parties have spent close to six million US dollars for campaigning. Spends can be attributed to road shows, online adds, cash, helicopters etc. India comes close on the heels of seven billion US dollars spent on the US 2012 presidential election.
2. The government this time raised the limits of spending per candidate from rupees 40 lakh to 70 lakh for most states in India.
3. 186 out of 543 MPs elected in the current Lok Sabha in 2014 have criminal cases against them.
4. Election commission of India reported that from the registered women voter base, 65 % women voted in elections 2014. This has significantly increased from women voter turnout back in 2009 which was 57.23 %. Furthermore, 11 % women candidates where elected in 2014, only 61 MPs from a total of 543 MPs elected are women.

Table 1.1: Voter turnout highlights of Lok Sabha elections 2014.

	Lok Sabha 2014	Lok Sabha 2009
Total votes polled in the Lok Sabha Election	55.38 crore	41.7 crore
Total Electorate	83.41 crore	71.69 crore
Total turnout %	66.38% highest ever	58.19 %
Women turnout	65.63 %	55.82%
Male turnout	67.09%	60.24%
Gender gap	1.46 % lowest ever	4.42%

Source: provisional data including postal ballots

The above table reveals that the 2014 Lok Sabha Election was handsome turnout of voters than 2009 elections , positive majority in both Male and Female ratio increased more than

10 % and close to 10 % voter turnout. Gender gap voter was a low percentage as it was 1.46 % in 2014 and 4.42 % in 2009.

Conclusion:

To conclude we can say that BJP recorded a historic win in the 2014 Lok Sabha election. It was able to secure 282 seats on its own and upto 335 with its allies. This election emphasizes the importance of youth power, because there is a very large increase in the number of new voters in our country. This election is very much expensive in terms of money from the previous elections.

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